

Devyāmata, śilānyāsalakṣaṇacaturāśītimapaṭalaḥ, edition.

N f87v, line 5; M Mf61v, line 5; Wf69r, line 2
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84.1 atah param viśeṣeṇa śilānyāsasya lakṣaṇam
mūlapādava pañcaiva kathyate śṛṇu sāmpratam

84.2 ādāv evaṃ samāseṇa śilālakṣaṇam uttamam
śilānyāsavīdhānam ca procyate tadanantaram

N f88r

84.3 śilā vātheṣṭakaṃ vāpi catasro lakṣaṇānvitāḥ
prāsādamūlapādaḥ tu nyastavyāḥ sumanoramāḥ

Mf62r

84.4 caturaśrāḥ samā bhadrāḥ samantād dhastasammitāḥ
vistarasya tribhāgena bāhalyena susammitāḥ

84.5 śilānām iṣṭakānām ca pramāṇam lakṣaṇam smṛtam
nandādyadhiṣṭhitā jñeyāḥ śilā vāpy athaveṣṭakāḥ

84.6 śilārūpāḥ smṛtā viddhyā nandādyāś ceṣṭakātmikāḥ
sampūrṇāḥ sutalāḥ snigdḥāḥ susvanā lakṣaṇānvitāḥ

84.7 kuśadūrvāṅkitā dhanyā dhvajacchatrasacāmarāḥ
aṅkuśatorāṇopetāḥ kūrmasamatsyahālānvitāḥ

Wf69v

84.8 darpaṇahastivajrāṅkāḥ praśastā dravyalāñchitāḥ
śastapakṣimṛgāntāś ca vṛṣāṅkāḥ sarvadā hitāḥ

N is illegible, due to folio damage, at 1ab.

After verse 2, M repeats 2cd: śilānyāsavīdhānantuprocayatetadanantaram.

Ω = NM(→W)

- 1c pādava] N; pādavaṃ M 2b uttamam] N; uttam M 3a vātheṣṭakaṃ] N; vāthekaṃ M
3d nyastavyāḥ] em.; nyastavyā NM • sumanoramāḥ] N; sumanoramā M
4a caturaśrāḥ] em.; caturaśrā NM • bhadrāḥ] em.; bhadrā NM 4b dhasta] N; dha M
4d susammitāḥ] em.; susammitā M; [****] N 5a śilānām iṣṭakānām] M; [*****]nāñ N
5b pramāṇam] N; pramāṇa M • lakṣaṇam] N; lakṣaṇa M 5c jñeyāḥ] em.; jñeyā NM
5d athaveṣṭakāḥ] N; athavekāḥ M 6b nandādyāś] N; nandadyā M
• ceṣṭakātmikāḥ] N; ce[-]kātmikāḥ M 6c sampūrṇāḥ] N; sampūrṇāḥ M
• snigdḥāḥ] N; snigdḥā M 7a dhanyā] N; dhānyā M 8a darpaṇa] em.; darpaṇam NM
8b praśastā] N; praśasta M • lāñchitāḥ] M; lāñchitā N 8c śasta] N; sasa M
• mṛgāntāś] M; mṛgāntāś N 8d vṛṣāṅkāḥ] em.; vṛṣāṅkā M; vṛṣākā N
• sarvadā] M; sacadā N • hitāḥ] N; hikāḥ M

- 84.9 svastikāvedikāyuktā nandyāvartyāṅkalakṣitāḥ
padmādīlakṣaṇopetāḥ śilāḥ sarvārthasiddhidāḥ
- 84.10 tathā govājipādāṅkāḥ śilā dhanyāḥ sukhāvahāḥ
kravyādāmṛgapādāṅkā na śastāḥ pakṣiṇām tathā
- 84.11 digmūḍhāvāhyahināś ca dīrghahrasvāḥ kṣatānvitāḥ
vivarṇāḥ sphuṭitā bhagnāḥ samtyajya lakṣaṇacyutāḥ
- 84.12 praśastaprāṇirūpāṅkāḥ praśastadravyalāñchitāḥ
yathoktalakṣaṇopetāḥ śilā nityam hitāvahāḥ
- 84.13 evam śilā samākhyātā lakṣaṇena samāsataḥ
iṣṭakānām samāsena lakṣaṇam śṛṇu sāmpratam
- 84.14 sutalā lakṣaṇopetāś catasro hastasammitāḥ
svapramāṇatribhāgena bāhalyena samanvitāḥ
- 84.15 ekavarṇāḥ supaktāś ca supramāṇā manoramāḥ
nandādyāś ceṣṭakāḥ kāryāś caturaśrāḥ susammitāḥ
- 84.16 āgneyyādikrameṇaiva nandādyā guṇalakṣaṇāḥ
yathoktalakṣaṇopetā vinyastā sarvadā hitāḥ

Mf62v

Wf70r

Ω = NM(→W)

- 9a vedikā] N; vedika M 9c padmādi] M; padmāni N 9d śilāḥ] em.; śilā N
• dāḥ] N; dā M 10b śilā] N; śila M • dhanyāḥ] em.; dhanyā N; dhānyā M
• sukhāvahāḥ] N; sukhāvahā M 10d śastāḥ] em.; śastā N; sastā M
11b dīrgha] N; dargha M 11c vivarṇāḥ] em.; vivarṇṇā{ḥ} M; vivarṇṇā N
• bhagnāḥ] em.; bhagnā NM
11d lakṣaṇacyutāḥ] em.; lakṣaṇ[ā]acyutāḥ N; lakṣaṇacyutā M
12a prāṇirūpāṅkāḥ] N; rūpaparyaṅkāḥ M 12b dravya] N; śabda M
• lāñchitāḥ] N; lāñcchitā M 13a samākhyātā] M; samākhyā N
13b samāsataḥ] N; samāsataḥ M 13d lakṣaṇam] N; lakṣaṇa M
14c tribhāgena] em.; tribhāgeṇana N; ṭribhāgenana M 14d bāhalyena] N; bāhalye M
15b manoramāḥ] em.; manoramā NM 15c nandādyāś] M; nandyādyāś N
15d aśrāḥ] N; aśrā M 16a āgneyyādi] em.; āgneyādi NM
6b nandādyā] M; naṃdyādyāḥ N 16c lakṣaṇopetā] em.; lakṣaṇohetā NM

- 84.17 aśastaprāṇipādānkāḥ chinnakarnāś ca varjitāḥ
asthyaṅgārānvitā neṣṭāḥ krṣṇavarṇāḥ saśarkarāḥ
- 84.18 mandapakṣā vipakṣāś ca bāhuhināś ca khaṇḍitāḥ
bhagnāś ca viṣamā hīnā varjanīyāḥ prayatnataḥ
- 84.19 evaṃ parīkṣya yatnena yathoktāḥ śubhalakṣaṇāḥ
vinyasec chāstravit prājñāḥ śilām vāpy athaveṣṭakām
- 84.20 ādhāro mūlapādasya śilānyāso yataḥ smṛtaḥ
tasmād ādau śilānyāso mūlapādasya kathyate
- 84.21 śilānyāsas tu kartavyaḥ prāsāde 'smiṃ cchilāmaye
iṣṭakānām tu vinyāsaḥ prāsāde ceṣṭakāmaye
- 84.22 śailaje śailajaḥ pīṭha aiṣṭake iṣṭakaḥ smṛtaḥ
śilānyāsādiko bhadre mūlapādo vidhīyate
- 84.23 śuklapakṣe sunakṣatre sutithau cottarāyaṇe
sthirarāśyudaye dhanye sugrahe karaṇe śubhe
- 84.24 yajamānānukūle ca saumyamitrāvalokite
svastipuṇyāhamaṅgalyair gītavāditraniśvanaiḥ

N f88v

Mf63r

Ω = NM(→W)

- 17c pādānkāḥ] N; pādānkā M 18b hīnāś] em.; nīnāś NM
- 18d varjanīyāḥ] em.; varjanīyā NM 19b yathoktāḥ] N; yathokta M
- śubhalakṣaṇāḥ] em.; śubhalakṣaṇā {ḥ} N; lakṣalakṣaṇā M
- 19c vinyasec chāstravit] N; vinyāśeśāstravit M • prājñāḥ] em.; prājñāḥ N; prājñā M
- 19d śilām] N; śilā M • vāpy] N; cāpy M • athaveṣṭakām] N; athaveṣṭakāḥ M
- 20c ādau] N; ādādu M 21a nyāsas] N; nyāsaṃ M
- kartavyaḥ] N; kartavya M 21d maye] N; mayet M
- 24c maṅgalyair] N; maṅgalye M

- 84.25 sthāpakas tu śuciḥ snātaḥ śāstrajñāḥ susamāhitaḥ
śuklamālādharāḥ prājñāḥ śuklagandhānulepanāḥ
- 84.26 kṛtadevārcano dhīraḥ śilānyāsaṃ samārabhet
nītvā sudikṣu nandādyāḥ prāsādasyaiiva vāstunaḥ
- 84.27 vedīm kṛtvā tu khātor dhvam caturaśrām tathākṣataiḥ
śilāḥ saṃsthāpayet tatra śilpidoṣaviśuddhaye
- 84.28 saṃsnāpya praṇavenādau snāpayed astravāriṇā
tataḥ saṃsnāpya saṃśodhya samyak chilācatuṣṭayam
- 84.29 tataḥ svanāmamantreṇa praṇavena prapūjayet
samyak prapūjya vijñāpya ekaikānām krameṇa tu
- 84.30 āgneyyādikrameṇaiva svadikstham avatārayet
tato 'vatārayitvā tu sthāpakaḥ śilpibhiḥ saha
- 84.31 vīkṣayet sūtramārgaṃ tu sūtreṇa sarvataḥ samam
kṛtvā tu śāstravit prājñāḥ śilāḥ karṇeṣu vinyaset
- 84.32 sūtradhārasamāḥ sarvāḥ kartavyāḥ sarvadā samāḥ
nandā bhadrā jayā pūrṇā ity etās catasraḥ śilāḥ

Wf70v

Mf63v

Ω = NM(→W)

- 25a tu] N; tuḥ M 25b susamāhitaḥ] N; susamāhitāḥ M
25c mālādharāḥ] N; mālādharā M 27a vedīm] N; devī M
• khātor dhvam] em; khātor ddhva NM 27b tathākṣataiḥ] M; tath[[au]]ākṣataiḥ N
27c śilāḥ] em.; śilā NM • saṃsthāpayet] N; saṃsthāpaye M
27d viśuddhaye] N; viśuddhayet M
28d samyak chilā] em.; samyakcchilā M; samyacchilā N
29b praṇavena] em.; praṇaveṇa N; praṇamyaca M
29c samyak prapūjya] conj.; samaṃmyakpūjya NM 29d ekaikānām] M; ekaikānā N
30a āgneyyādi] N; āgneyādi M 30c tu] M; tu[[h]] N
30d śilpibhiḥ saha] em.; śilpibhissaha N; śilpibhiḥsahaḥ M
31a vīkṣayet] N; vīkṣaye M 31b sarvataḥ] em.; sarvatas N; sarvata M
31c prājñāḥ] N; prajñāḥ M 31d śilāḥ] conj.; śilām N; śilā M 32a dhāra] N; dhārā M
32b kartavyāḥ] N; kartavyā M 32c nandā] M; dandā N

84.33 āgneyyādiṣu nandādyāḥ sthātavyās tāḥ krameṇa tu
śilāyāḥ sthāpane samyak prathamāyā vicakṣaṇaḥ

Wf71r

84.34 śakunādinimittāni lagnaṃ caiva nirūpayet
vāstukaṇṣasamāḥ kāryā vāstudhārāsusammitāḥ

84.35 evaṃ susammitāḥ sarvāḥ kartavyā niścalāḥ śilāḥ
prāguttaraplavāḥ śastā nāparadakṣiṇaplavāḥ

84.36 suplavā niścalāḥ śastāḥ paridhikaṇṣasammitāḥ
tataḥ susaṃyato mantrī sthāpakaḥ śilpibhiḥ saha

84.37 dharākaraṇasamāṃ kṛtvā ekaikaṃ sthāpayet kramāt
vedavāditranirghoṣair gītamaṅgalavācakaiḥ

84.38 astratoyena saṃsnāpya snāpayen mantravāriṇā
divyarūpāḥ śilāḥ sarvā hemavarṇasubhūṣaṇāḥ

84.39 sarvābharaṇasampannāḥ parituṣṭāḥ smitānanāḥ
dhyātvā cāvāhayen mantrī ekaikāṃ mantratanmayām

N f89r

84.40 nandāvācādyam saṃsthāpya snāpayen mantravāriṇā
kāñcanai rājataiḥ kumbhais tāmrajair vāripūritaiḥ

Ω = NM(→W)

- 33a āgneyyādiṣu] N; āgneyādiṣu M 33d vicakṣaṇaḥ] N: vicakṣaṇāḥ M
34c karṇa] em.; karṇṇās N; karṇṇā[[ḥ]] M • kāryā] M; kāryāḥ N
35a susammitāḥ] N; susaṃmitā M 35c plavāḥ] N; plavā M
36a niścalāḥ] M; niścalās N 36d sthāpakaḥ] N; sthapakaḥ M • saha] N; sahaḥ M
37a dharā] M; dharāṃ N • samāṃ] N; samā M 37b ekaikaṃ] N; ekai M
37c vāditranirghoṣair] N; vāditrayanirghoṣa M
38ab saṃsnāpya snāpayen] em.; saṃsnāpyasnaṃpaye N; saṃsnāpayet M
38b vāriṇā] N; vāriṇāḥ M 38c rūpāḥ śilāḥ] em.; rūpāśilā NM
39a sampannāḥ] em.; sampannā NM 39b pari] M; papari N
• smitānanāḥ] N; smitānanā M 39c cāvāhayen] em.; cāvāhayet NM
39d ekaikāṃ] em.; ekaikā NM
• mantratanmayām] em.; mantratatanmayām N; mātratatanmayā M
40a vācādyam] em.; vācādyā NM 40b snāpayen] em.; snāpayet N; snāpaye M
40c rājataiḥ kumbhais] em.; rājatairkumbhais M; rā[****] N
40d tāmrajair] em.; tāmrajai M; [***]r N

- 84.41 mṛṇmayair vā navaiḥ śastaiḥ sudṛḍhaiḥ pallavānvitaiḥ
hiranyaūśadhisamyuktaiḥ praśastagandhacarcitaiḥ Mf64r
- 84.42 sragmālāpallavopetair yathoktalakṣaṇānvitaiḥ
āgneyyām ādito nandāṃ snāpayen mantravāriṇā Wf71v
- 84.43 snāpayet praṇavenaiva samyag nāmānvitena tu
evaṃ bhadrāṃ jayāṃ pūrṇāṃ snāpayed vidhivān guruḥ
- 84.44 tataḥ susnāpya vai nandāṃ vastreṇa toyam uddharet
vastraṃ kalpya tatas tasyāś candanena sugandhinā
- 84.45 vilipyā sarvato nandāṃ sugandhaiḥ puṣpadāmakaiḥ
pūjayitvā tato nandāṃ dhūpayitvā prapūrayet
- 84.46 mudrāṃ badhvā tatas tasyā naivedyaṃ saṃnivedayet
dadhi māṃsādikaṃ sarvanivedyaṃ saṃprasādayet
- 84.47ab praṇavena svamantreṇa sambodhena prasādhayet

Ω = NM(→W)

- 41a mṛṇ] N; mṛt M • navaiḥ] em.; navaiś N; navai M 41d praśasta] N; prastastā M
42c āgneyyām] N; āgneyam M • nandāṃ] N; nandā M 42d snāpayen] em.; snāpayet
MN
• vāriṇā] N; vāriṇāḥ M 43a praṇavenaiva] N; praṇavenneva M 43c bhadrāṃ
jayāṃ pūrṇāṃ] em.; bhadrāṃjayāṃpūrṇāṃ N; bhadrājayāpūrṇā M 43d vidhivān]
em.; vidhivā NM
44a nandāṃ] em.; nandā M; naṇdā N 45a nandāṃ] N; nandā M
45c nandāṃ] em.; nandā M; [**] N 45d dhūpayitvā] em.; dhūpayitvāḥ M; [****] N
46a mudrāṃ badhvā] em.; mudrāmbadhvā N; mudrāmvathā M • tatas] N; tatos M
46b saṃnivedayet] M; sannivedyayet N 46c māṃsādikaṃ] em.; māṃsādikaṃ N;
māsādikaṃ M
47b prasādhayet] N; prasārayet M

84.47cd ūṃ nande nandini puṃsāṃ tvāṃ atra sthāpayāmy aham

84.48 asmin saṃtiṣṭha tvaṃ hr̥ṣṭā yāvad ā candratāarakam
āyuh kāmam śriyaṃ nande tadā hi sarvadā nṛṇām

84.49 asmin rakṣā tvayā kāryā prāsāde yatnataḥ sadā
evaṃ vidhividhānajño bhadradīnām krameṇa tu

84.50 sthāpanam samprakurvīta mantras tāsām ihocyate
ūṃ bhadre sarvadā bhadram puṃsāṃ kuru hitāvahā

84.51 āyurdā kāmādā devi śrīpradā sarvadā bhava
ūṃ jaye sarvadā bhadre saṃtiṣṭha sthāpitā mayā

Mf64v

84.52ab nityam jayāvahā devi svāmiṇaḥ śrīpradā bhava

Ω = NM(→W)

After sarva, at 84.51b, W fails to copy an entire folio from M, resuming the record at 85.14a.

With 84.47c-49b, compare SŚ 4.1.102-103, Brunner 1998: 64:

oṃ nande nandini puṃsāṃ tvāmatra sthāpayāmyaham |
prāsāde tiṣṭha saṃhr̥ṣṭā yāvaccandrārkatāarakam ||
āyuskāmam śriyaṃ nande dehi vāsiṣṭhi dehinām |
asmin rakṣā sadā kāryā prāsāde yatnatastvayā |

With 84.50c-51b, compare SŚ 4.1.104, Brunner 1998: 64:

oṃ bhadre sarvadā bhadram lokānām kuru kāśyapi |
āyurdā kāmādā devi śrīpradā ca sadā bhava ||

With 84.51c-52b, compare SŚ 4.1.105, Brunner 1998: 64:

oṃ jaye'tra sadā devi tiṣṭha tvaṃ sthāpitā mayā |
nityam jayāya bhūtyai ca svāmīno bhava bhārgavi ||

47c nandini] N; nandinī M

47d atra] em.; antra NM

48a saṃtiṣṭha] M; satiṣṭha N • tvaṃ] N; tva M

48c śriyaṃ] N; śriya M

49b yatnataḥ] em.; yatnatas NM

49c vidhividhānajño] N; vidhividhānago M

49d krameṇa] N; krame M

50a sthāpanam] N; sthāpana M

50b mantras] M; mantraḥ N • tāsām] N; tāsāsm M

50d puṃsāṃ] em.; puṃsā MN

51a āyur] N; āyu M

51b bhava] N; bhavaḥ M

51c bhadre] N; bhadra M

51d saṃtiṣṭha] M; satiṣṭha N

52b svāmiṇaḥ] N; svāmīna M • bhava] N; bhavaḥ M

84.52cd ūṃ pūrṇe tvaṃ mahāvidye sarvasaṃdohalakṣaṇe

84.53 sarvasaṃpūrṇam evātra prāsāde kuru sampadā
evaṃ prasādyā nandādyā vāstudevādhipaṃ yajet

84.54 nivedya vāstupataye dadyād bhūtabaliṃ tataḥ
evaṃ saṃsthāpitā bhadre nandādyā na vicālayet

84.55 cālāne bahavo doṣāḥ susthītau bahavo guṇāḥ
evaṃ saṃsthāpitaṃ tato noddharen na ca cchindayet

84.56 evaṃ mūlacayaṃ kuryāt kṛtvā salilam antagam
grāme vā nagare vāpi grhaprāsādayos tathā

84.57 śīlānyāsaḥ samākhyāto mūlapādacayaṃ śṛṇu

iti śīlānyāsalakṣaṇacaturāśītimapaṭalaḥ

Ω = NM(→W)

After sarva, at 84.51b, W fails to copy an entire folio from M, resuming the record at 85.14a.

With 84.52c-53b, compare SŚ 4.1.101, Brunner 1998: 63:

oṃ pūrṇe tvaṃ mahāvidye sarvasandohalakṣaṇe |
sarvaṃ saṃpūrṇamevātra kuruṣvāṅgīrasaḥ sute ||

52c pūrṇe] N; pūrṇa M

53b sampadā] N; sarvvadā M

54a nivedya] N; nivedyā M

54b dadyād] N; dadyā M

55a doṣāḥ] em.; doṣā NM

55c saṃsthāpitaṃ] N; saṃsthāpitas M

• tato] conj.; tatsan NM

56a cayam] N; cayā M • kuryāt] em.; kuryā NM

56b antagam] conj.; antalam MN

57a samākhyāto] N; samākhyātā M

57b cayam] N; cayā M

• śṛṇu] N; śṛṇuḥ M

after 57 iti śīlānyāsalakṣaṇacaturāśītimapaṭalaḥ] M; iti śīlānyāsapaṭalaḥ N